

O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI MILLIY QONUNCHILIK TIZIMIDA YOSHLARNI MA’NAViy-MAFKURAVIY TAHDIDLARDAN HIMOYA QILISH MASALALARI.

Mo‘ydinov Asilbek Adxam o‘g‘li

Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar kafedrasasi o‘qtuvchisi

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Annotatsiya. Keyingi yillarda ayrim yoshlarda millatga, Vatanga foyda keltirishni o‘ylash, mustaqillikni mustahkamlashda foydali inson bo‘lib yetishish hissi maxsus, ilmiy asosda shakllantirilmaganligi tufayli shaxsiy manfaatni o‘ylash, yengil yo‘llar bilan to‘kis xayotga intilish hissi namoyon bo‘lmoqda. Shu bilan birga ayrim fuqarolar orasida ma’naviy cheklanganlik, dunyoqarashning torligi, milliy odob meyorlariga rioya qilmaslik, so‘z va ish orasidagi tafovut, milliy g‘ururning sustligi kabi noxush ko‘rinishlar uchrab turadiki, ularni birgalashib bartaraf qilish lozim.

Kalit so‘zlar: axborot, g‘oyalar, fikr, so‘z, internet provayderlari.

ISSUES OF PROTECTING YOUTH FROM SPIRITUAL AND IDEOLOGICAL THREATS IN THE NATIONAL LEGISLATIVE SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.

Abstract. In the following years, some young people have a feeling of thinking about benefiting the nation, the motherland, of growing up to be a useful person in strengthening independence, of thinking about personal benefit, of striving for peace in light ways, due to the fact that it is not formed on a special, scientific basis. At the same time, such unpleasant manifestations as spiritual limitation, narrowness of the worldview, non-observance of national decency, discrepancy between word and work, lack of national pride are encountered among some citizens, which should be eliminated together.

Key words: information, ideas, opinion, word, internet providers.

ВОПРОСЫ ЗАЩИТЫ МОЛОДЕЖИ ОТ ДУХОВНО-ИДЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ УГРОЗ В СИСТЕМЕ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОГО ЗАКОНОДАТЕЛЬСТВА РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН.

Аннотация. В последующие годы у некоторых молодых людей проявляется чувство личной заинтересованности, стремление к полноценной жизни легкими путями, в связи с тем, что у них не сформировано на специальной, научной основе чувство взросления полезным человеком в укреплении независимости, в том, чтобы приносить пользу нации, Родине. Вместе с тем, среди отдельных граждан встречаются такие неприятные проявления, как моральная ограниченность, узость мировоззрения, несоблюдение критериев Национального этикета, несоответствие между словом и делом, слабость национальной гордости, которые необходимо преодолевать сообща.

Ключевое слова: Информация, идеи, мнение, слово, интернет-провайдеры.

Xorijiy davlatlarning tajribasi shuni ko‘rsatdiki, yoshlarni Internetdan himoya qilish milliy qonunchilikni rivojlantirish orqali amalga oshiriladi. Huquqiy davlat qurmoqchi bo‘lgan davlat albatta milliy qonuchiligida bu kabi taxdidlarni oldini olishga qaratilgan huquqiy normalar bo‘lishi talab etiladi. Avvalo internetdan kelayotgan taxdidlarni oldini olish uchun davlat internet tarmog‘ini nazorat qila olish imkoniyati va internetning barcha imkoniyatlarini tushuna oladigan yetuk mutaxasislarni mavjud bo‘lishi talab etiladi. Davlatimiz mustaqillikning dastlabki yillaridan boshlab bu soxada bir qator ishlarni amalga oshirdi. Jumladan, 1995 yil 29 aprelda «UZ»domeniga

asos solindi. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Markaziy Bankining ma’lumotlarini banklararo uzatish tarmog‘i ishga tushdi. 1996 yil. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasi huzurida BMTning O‘zbekistonda Internetni rivojlantirish loyihasi tashkil etildi. Keyinchalik bu UzNet nomi bilan tanilgan. Telekommunikatsiya bozorida UzPAK kompaniyasi faoliyatini boshladi.

Mamlakatimizda bu soxa bo‘yicha malakali kadrlar tayyorlash maqsadida 2002 yil 30 may kuni O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Birinchi Prezidenti I.Karimovning PF-3080 Farmoniga binoan Toshkent elektrotexnika aloqa instituti Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universitetiga aylantirildi. 2005 yil 2 iyun kuni soha mutaxassislarini salmog‘ini yanada oshirish maqsadida O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Birinchi Prezidenti I.Karimovning PQ-91 sonli Qaroriga qabul qilindi. Qarorga ko‘ra Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universitetining Qarshi, Samarqand, Urganch va Farg‘ona shaharlarida mintaqaviy filiallar tashkil etildi.

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi o‘zining internet milliy “uz” domeni domeniga ega bo‘ldi. Shu o‘rinda milliy uz domeni xususida to‘xtalsak. Yuqori darajali «UZ» domeni 1995 yil 29 aprelda ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

2019 yilning 5 noyabr’ xolati bo‘yicha uz domenida ro‘yxatdan o‘tgan veb-saytlar soni 71 mingta bo‘lgan bo‘lsa. 2016 yilning shu davri bilan solishtirilganda, milliy domenning o‘shish sur‘ati 130 % yuqori www.uz milliy qidiruv tizimi katalogida ro‘yxatgan o‘tgan elektron axborot resurslar soni 30 ming atrofida bo‘lib, ularga tashrif buyuruvchi oylik Internet foydalanuvchilari soni 51 milliondan oshgan. Qiyosiy tahlil qilsak, www.uz ilk marotaba 1995 yil 29 aprel kuni ro‘yxatga olingan. 2010 yil 25 fevral holatiga ko‘ra Milliy internet hududida 11 mingta veb-sayt faoliyat ko‘rsatgan bo‘lsa, 2016 yilda ular soni 26 mingdan, 2019 yilda 71 mingdan oshgan. Ko‘rinib turibdiki yildan yilga internetdan foydalanuvchilar soni keskin oshib bormoqda. Buning natijasida jamiyat va davlatning oldida bir qator muammolar yuzaga keldi. Bular – globall internet taxdidlaridir.

Mamlakatimiz axolini ayniqsa yoshlarni internetdagi taxdidlardan ximoyalash maqsadida bir qator muxim ishlarni amalga oshirdi. Jumladan, milliy qonunchilik bazamizga bu kabi taxdidlarni oldini olishga xizmat qiluvchi huquqiy normalar kiritildi.

Tahlillar shuni ko‘rsatmoqdaki, keyingi yillarda ayrim yoshlarda millatga, Vatanga foyda keltirishni o‘ylash, mustaqillikni mustahkamlashda foydali inson bo‘lib yetishish hissi maxsus, ilmiy asosda shakllantirilmaganligi tufayli shaxsiy manfaatni o‘ylash, yengil yo‘llar bilan to‘kis xayotga intilish hissi namoyon bo‘lmoqda. Shu bilan birga ayrim fuqarolar orasida ma’naviy cheklanganlik, dunyoqarashning torligi, milliy odob meyorlariga rioya qilmaslik, so‘z va ish orasidagi tafovut, milliy g‘ururning sustligi kabi noxush ko‘rinishlar uchrab turadiki, ularni birgalashib bartaraf qilish lozim.

Ayni paytda ba’zi yoshlarimiz turli yot g‘oyalarni xolis axborot manbai sifatida qabul qilayotganini ham e’tibordan qochirmaslik kerak. Shunday ekan, yoshlarimiz yot mafkuralarning “mehribonligi”, “xolisligi”, “do‘stonaligi” ortida nima yotganini chuqur anglab olishi lozim. Ya’ni, ularning zamirida muntazam o‘zgarib turuvchi jonsarak aqidaparastlik targ‘iboti turganini tushunib borish kerak.

Tarixga nazar tashlaydigan bo‘lsak, ota-bobolarimiz bir paytlar baland tepaliklarga chiqib, olov yoqib, yog‘iyni bostirib kelayotganligidan bir-birlarini ogoh qilishgan, ya’ni axborot uzatishgan. Bugun esa manzara mutlaqo boshqacha. Taraqqiyot shiddatli tarzda ildamlab

borayotgan hozirgi zamonda kichkinagina bitta xonada o'tirib, bir necha daqiqalar ichida butun dunyoga turli xildagi axborotlarni tarqatish mumkin. Bir so'z bilan aytganda, olam va odam yuksak taraqqiyot asnosida juda o'tkir, ta'bir joiz bo'lsa, global muammolar bilan ro'paro kelmoqda .

Jamiyatning o'z ertasi va kelajagiga ishonchi o'z-o'zidan hosil bo'lmaydi. Buning zamirida millat baxt saodati yo'lida, demak xar bir fuqaro manfaatidan kelib chiquvchi maxsus faoliyat - mafkuraviy tarbiya yotadi. Mafkuraviy tarbiya deganda gap, «kishilar dunyoqarashini boshqarish xaqida emas, balki odamlarning tafakkurini boyitish, uni yangi ma'no va mazmun bilan to'ldirish»ni ham anglatadi.

Mafkuraviy tortishuvlarda tahdid soluvchi ham, o'zini himoya qiluvchi ham - g'oyani ommalashtirish uslublaridan foydalanadi. Bu - mafkuraviy tarbiya uslublaridir. Demak, qaysi tomonning yengishini pirovard natijada ilmga asoslangan targ'ibot va tashviqot hal qiladi. Shu tariqa mafkuralar tortishuvi - targ'ibot va tashviqotlar tortishuviga aylanadi, deyish mumkin. Shu sababli «Milliy istiqlol mafkurasi tom ma'nodagi milliy mafkuraga aylanish uchun qator talablarga javob berishi zarur. Ana shunday talablardan biri - har qanday yovuz g'oyaga qarshi javob bera olishidir .

Buning uchun esa mafkuraviy profilaktikani kuchaytirish zarur. Mafkuraviy profilaktika – ijtimoiy institutlar tomonidan amalga oshiriladigan turli shakllardagi g'oyaviy –tarbiyaviy, ma'naviy-mafkuraviy ishlar majmui bo'lib, u butun g'oyaviy tarbiya tizimini qamrab oladi. Mafkuraviy profilaktika g'oyaviy bo'shliqni bartaraf etish, mafkuraviy parokandalikni oldini olish yoki biror-bir hudud, qatlam, guruhni yot va zararli g'oyalar ta'siridan xalos qilish maqsadida amalga oshiriladi . Mafkuraviy profilaktika quyidagi xususiyatlari bilan ajralib turadi:

Birinchidan, muayyan maqsadlarni amalga oshirish maqsadida bir-biriga uzviy bog'langan qator tashkiliy tuzilmalarning ketma-ketligi ekanligi;

Ikkinchidan, o'zining tugal maqsadlari sari yetaklovchi, ularni amalga oshirishini ta'min etuchi ilmiy asoslangan harakat dasturiga ega ekanligi bilan o'ziga xoslik kasb etadi.

Dunyo shiddat bilan o'zgarib, barqarorlik va xalqlarning mustaxkam rivojlanishiga raxna soladigan turli yangi taxdid va xavflar paydo bo'layotgan bugungi kunda ma'naviyat va ma'rifatga, axloqiy tarbiya, yoshlarning bilim olish, kamolga yetishga intilishiga e'tibor qaratish xar qachongidan xam muximdir. Yoshlarni “ommaviy madaiyat”ning salbiy ta'siridan himoya qilish bugungi kunning eng dolzarb vazifasi bo'lib qolmoqda. Buning uchun eng avvalo ularni milliy tiklanish g'oyasi, milliy madaniyat va qadriyatlarni e'zozlash ruhida tarbiyalash, yoshlarni axborot-resurs markazlariga, madaniy-tarixiy yodgorlik maskanlariga, teatr va ko'rgazmalarga jalb etish, barkamol avlodni bilimli, sog'lom va yuksak ma'naviy-axloqiy fazilatga ega insonlar qilib tarbiyalash, ular ongi va qalbida mafkuraviy immunitetni shakllantirishda barcha birday ma'sulyatni his etmog'i lozim.

Binobarin, o'sib kelayotgan avlodni shunday tarbiyalashimiz kerakki, ular axborot makoniga kiranda, faqat o'zi uchun zarur va foydali narsani olsin, Internetdan foydalanish madaniyatini o'rgansin. Bu masalada Internet tizimi orqali mentalitetimizga mutlaqo yot mafkura va dunyoqarashni yoshlarimiz qalbi, ongiga singdirishga urinayotganlar borligi, ayniqsa, xatarli ekanligidan barchamiz ogox bo'lishimiz zarur.

Davlatimiz internet taxdidlariga eng ko'p tushib qolayotgan qatlam ya'ni yoshlar qatlamini ximoyalash maqsadida 2016 yil 14 sentyabr kuni “Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosati to'g'risida” gi

O‘zbekiston Respublikasining qonunini qabul qildi. Unda yoshlarga ta’luqli bo‘lgan barcha masalalar qamrab olindi. Bu qonunning asosiy yo‘nalishi etib quyidagilar belgilandi:

- yoshlarning huquqlari, erkinliklari va qonuniy manfaatlarini ta’minlash;
- yoshlarning hayoti va sog‘lig‘ini saqlash;
- yoshlarning ma’naviy, intellektual, jismoniy va axloqiy jihatdan kamol topishiga ko‘maklashish;
- yoshlar uchun ochiq va sifatli ta’limni ta’minlash;
- yoshlarni ishga joylashtirish va ularning bandligi uchun shart-sharoitlar yaratish;
- yoshlarni vatanparvarlik, fuqarolik tuyg‘usi, bag‘rikenglik, qonunlarga, milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlarga hurmat ruhida, zararli ta’sirlar va oqimlarga qarshi tura oladigan, hayotga bo‘lgan qat’iy ishonch va qarashlarga ega qilib tarbiyalash;
- yoshlarni axloqiy negizlarni buzishga olib keladigan xatti-harakatlardan, terrorizm va diniy ekstremizm, separatizm, fundamentalizm, zo‘ravonlik va shafqatsizlik g‘oyalariidan himoya qilish;
- yoshlarning huquqiy ongi va huquqiy madaniyati darajasini yuksaltirish;
- iqtidorli va iste’dodli yoshlarni qo‘llab-quvvatlash hamda rag‘batlantirish;
- yoshlar tadbirkorligini rivojlantirish uchun shart-sharoitlar yaratish;
- yoshlarda sog‘lom turmush tarziga intilishni shakllantirish, shuningdek yoshlarning bo‘sh vaqtlarini mazmunli tashkil etish va yoshlar sportini ommaviy rivojlantirish uchun shart-sharoitlar yaratish;
- yosh oilalarni ma’naviy va moddiy jihatdan qo‘llab-quvvatlash, ular uchun munosib uy-joy va ijtimoiy-maishiy sharoitlarni yaratish bo‘yicha kompleks chora-tadbirlar tizimini amalga oshirish;
- yoshlarning huquqlari va erkinliklarini ro‘yobga chiqarish sohasida faoliyatni amalga oshiruvchi xalqaro tashkilotlar bilan hamkorlikni rivojlantirish.

Bu qonun bilan davlatimizda Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosatini ro‘yobga chiqarishda ishtirok etuvchi organlar va muassasalarning faoliti belgilab qo‘yildi. Yoshlar masalasi bilan barcha bo‘g‘indagi raxbarlarni shug‘ullanishi kerakligi bu qonun bilan mustaxkamlab qo‘yildi. Yoshlarni tarbiyasi bilan shug‘ullanishga qaratilgan huquqiy baza yana ham mustaxkamlandi. Bilamizki xozirgi kunda O‘zbekistonning dunyo tan olgan ulkan yutuqlarning asosida inson omili turibdi. Buyuk marifatparvar Abdulla Avloniyning “Tarbiya biz uchun yo hayot – yo mamot, yo najot – yo halokat, yo saodat – yo falokat masalasidir”, degan so‘zlari bir asr oldin qanday axamiyat kasb etgan bo‘lsa xozirgi kunimizda xam o‘z axamiyatini yo‘qotmagan. Ma’lumot olish va uni tarqatishda hozirgi kunda internet tarmog‘i asosiy vosita sifatida xizmat qilmoqda. “Axborot erkinligi prinsiplari va kafolatlari to‘g‘risida”gi O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Qonunining 14-moddasi talablariga ko‘ra, qonunga xilof ravishda ijtimoiy ongga axborot vositasida ruhiy ta’sir ko‘rsatishga, uni chalg‘itishga yo‘l qo‘yilmaydi. Shuningdek, jamiyatning ma’naviy, madaniy va tarixiy boyliklarini, mamlakatning ilmiy va ilmiy-texnikaviy salohiyatini asrash hamda rivojlantirish; milliy o‘zlikni anglashni izdan chiqarishga, jamiyatni tarixiy va milliy an’analar hamda urf-odatlardan uzoqlashtirishga, ijtimoiy-siyosiy vaziyatni beqarorlashtirishga, millatlararo va konfessiyalararo totuvlikni buzishga qaratilgan axborotlarni tarqatish xam taqiqlanadi.

“O‘zbekiston Respublikasida “Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosatining asoslari to‘g‘risida”gi O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Qonunining 6-moddasida e’shlar orasida odob-axloqni buzishga, shu

jumladan, haësizlikni va shafqatsizlikni tashviqot qilishga qaratilgan har qanday xatti-harakat man etilishi belgilab qo'yilgan. "Bola huquqlarining kafolatlari to'g'risida"gi O'zbekiston Respublikasi Qonunining 16-moddasi talablariga ko'ra, har bir voyaga yetmagan mushtariy ommaviy axborot vositalarida axloqiy va ma'naviy kamol topishiga ziyon yetkazmaydigan axborot olish huquqiga ega. Xozirgi kunimizda ko'ryapmizki arzimmas tuyulgan bir xabar xam globalashuv ta'siridan kuch olib jamiyatga ko'plab tahdidlarni keltirib chiqarmoqda. O'zbekiston Respublikasining "Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosati to'g'risida"gi Qonunida yoshlar orasida odob axloqni buzishga, shu jumladan, zo'ravonlik, hayosizlik, va shafqatsizlikni targ'ib qilishga qaratilgan har qanday xatti-harakatlar, "Bola huquqlarining kafolatlari to'g'risida"gi Qonunda esa behayollik, shafqatsizlik va zo'ravonlik haqida hikoya qiluvchi, inson qadr-qimmatini tahqirlovchi, bolalarga zararli ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi va huquqbuzarliklar sodir etishlariga sabab bo'luvchi adabiyotlarni tarqatish, fil'mlarni namoyish etishning taqiqlanishi belgilanib qo'yilgan. Bu kabi taxdidlarga qarshi xar tomonlama chuqur o'ylangan, ilmiy asosda puxta tashkil etilgan, uzluksiz olib boriladigan ma'naviy tarbiya bilan javob berish tizimi yaratildi.

Milliy qonunchilik tajribasida bu kabi normalarning aks etishi yoshlarimizga turli axborot xurujlari, jamiyatimizga yot bo'lgan g'oyalarga nisbatan mafkuraviy immunitetni shakllantirishda, farzandlarimizni xalqimizning milliy ma'naviyati, oilalarimizda aml qilinadigan tartib qoidalarga, ota-onaga hurmat ruhi asosida tarbiyalashda muhim ahamiyatga egadir.

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